

INTER-CHANNEL SYNCHRONISATION FOR TRANSMITTING LIVE AUDIO STREAMS OVER DIGITAL RADIO LINKS

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ABSTRACT

There are two key challenges to the use of digital, wireless communication links for the short-range transmission of multiple, live music streams from independent sources: delay and synchronisation. Delay is a result of the necessary buffering in digital music streams, and digital signal processing. Lack of synchronisation between time-stamped streams is a result of independent analogue-to-digital conversion clocks. Both of these effects are barriers to the wireless, digital recording studio.

In this paper we explore the issue of synchronization, presenting a model, some network performance figures, and the results of experiments to explore the perceived effects of losing synchronization between channels. We also explore how this can be resolved in software when the data is streamed over a Wi-Fi link for real-time audio monitoring using consumer-grade equipment. We show how both fixed and varying offsets between channels can be resolved in software, to below the level of perception, using an offset-merge algorithm. As future work, we identify some of the key solutions for automated calibration.

The contribution of this paper is the presentation of perception experiments for mixing unsynchronized music channels, the development of a model representing how these streams can be synchronized after-the-fact, and the presentation of current work in progress in terms of realizing the model.

INTRODUCTION

One of the key challenges for the digital music studio is communicating the digitized sound data from the sources (instruments and microphones) to the mixing-desk for recording. The benefits are the removal of physical wiring, and increased flexibility; but the challenges due to increased latency and inter-channel synchronization are not insignificant.

Published results show that a delay between the visual

and sound data of over 1.4-42ms is apparent [1] (for example, to a sound engineer on the recording desk). Even though Interaural Time Difference (ITD) is a well known phenomenon, there is less published work on the impact on the listener on inter-channel synchronization errors, and how to resolve them. In this paper we review related work, present our experimental results on the audibility of inter-channel synchronization errors, and present a solution showing that these errors can be reduced below a perceptible margin.

RELATED WORK

How a time delay between receiving a sound in the ears (ITD) is processed is explored in the original Jeffress Model [2] and more recent refinements (e.g. [3,4,5]). The ability to detect ITD and its effect on the localization of the sound source has been explored in many papers (e.g. [6], [7], and [8]) and a good overview of the research is presented in [9].

Sound spatialization for listeners is caused by both interaural intensity (IIT) and time differences (ITD) [8]. In trying to understand the impact of de-synchronization between digital audio streams, we are only concerned with ITD. The apparent offset is frequency dependent (e.g. as discussed in [11]), but approximations from [5] are shown for frequencies below 500Hz (Equation 1) and above 2kHz (Equation 2), for an incident angle θ as shown in Figure 1. ITD is the inter-aural time difference, a is the head radius, c is the speed of the sound, and θ (in radians) is the incident angle shown in Figure 1. The angle θ is the perceived difference in the angle from which the sound is sourced (with respect to 0° indicating no synchronization error).

$$ITD_{500Hz} = (a/c)2 \sin \theta \quad (1)$$

$$ITD_{2kHz} = (a/c)(\theta + \sin \theta) \quad (2)$$

The consequences of this are that if two channels are not correctly synchronized, then an artificial apparent movement ($\hat{\theta}$) of the sound's source will result¹.

There are a number of different figures published for the Just Noticeable Difference (JND): for example in [12] a range of 10-20 μ s is presented, and 15 μ s in [13].

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¹ For low frequencies, $\theta = \sin^{-1}\{ITD/(2a/c)\}$
 $\approx ITD/(2a/c)$ for small angles

Figure 1. Sound Localisation Geometry.

The area of Networking Musical Performance (NMP) where physically remote musicians can play together is receiving significant research interest [14,15,16]. High latency introduces significant problems, specifically in terms of maintaining tempo [17]. The issues here are to do with synchronizing one’s own performance with the other participants – and typical acceptable figures for latency an order of magnitude larger than the ITD figures (30-90 ms [17], 50-65ms [18]) – with larger latencies tolerable for slower tempi.

A significant amount of work has been done on using correlation to identify inter-signal time shifts (for example in [19]). In this paper we focus on the re-synchronisation problem.

PERCEPTION OF ITD

As discussed in the previous section, there has been considerable research into exploring the limits of perception of ITD effects. However, much of this has used artificial or generated signals, for example [6,7,8,20,21], designed to explore the limits of human perception. Relating these results to the problem of un-synchronised music channels is not straightforward. Some examples using real-world signals are an extensive investigation into the comb filtering effect of inter-signal delays [19], the effect of latency on monitoring [1], and the effects of latency on remote music performance [14].

In this section we present the results of an experiment specifically designed to explore the limits of perception for two unsynchronized music channels. The purpose is to establish a baseline for the time-accuracy required in re-synchronising channels. The results of the experiment are presented for a number of listeners (using headphones). There are two key apparent effects: a shift in the apparent localization of the source, and an apparent change in the volume of the earlier stream.

The experimental setup consisted of preparing four different samples of three different stereo music recordings. Each of the four samples had a different delay introduced for the right channel (varying from 0 to 6 samples at 44,100 samples/second: 0 to 136 μ s), using the Audacity *Time Shift Tool*, as shown in Figure 2.

In a limited experiment, three different volunteers (the columns labeled 1,2,3 in Table 1) were used for the experiment, with varying degrees of experience in music. The volunteers were asked whether they could perceive a

shift in the apparent source of the sound (or any other difference in the sound experience, such as the relative volume, or other qualitative effects). This was reported on a scale of 0 (no perceivable difference with respect to the 0-sample shift recording) to 10 (a very noticeable shift that required no concentration to perceive) – these results are the figures shown in Table 1. The 0 figures shown for the 0-shift recording just represent the fact that this is the baseline against which the other recordings are compared.

Figure 2. Channel Offsets.

The results, shown in Table 1, indicate that a shift of 45.35 μ s was not perceivable, a shift of 90.1 μ s was just perceivable, and a shift of 136 μ s was clearly perceivable for this sample group.

Title	Shift ²	Perceived		
		1	2	3
Andrea Bocelli and Elisa <i>La Voce Del Silenzio</i> from <i>Vivere</i>	0	0	0	0
	2	1	5	0
	4	8	9	5
	6	10	10	10

Title	Shift	Perceived		
		1	2	3
Queen <i>We are the Champions</i> from <i>Absolute Greatest</i>	0	0	0	0
	2	0	4	0
	4	7	5	5
	6	10	10	10

Title	Shift	Perceived		
		1	2	3
Vivaldi <i>Larghetto from Concerto Grosso OP. 3/8 in A-Minor</i> from <i>Famous Concertos</i>	0	0	0	0
	2	2	6	0
	4	8	10	5
	6	10	10	10

Table 1. Experimental Perception Results.

² Shift is measured in samples at 44,100 samples-per-second: 1 sample=22.676 μ s

The conclusions drawn from these results are that synchronisation between the channels needs to be maintained within a window of at least $50\mu\text{s}$ in order to not introduce perceivable effects into a stereo music stream. Note that this is less than 3 samples at 44kHz, or less than 10 samples at 192kHz. Obviously, a larger sample group is required to determine a more robust figure. We will take this figure as our initial target for synchronisation; part of our future work is to do similar experiments for a larger selection of listeners.

SYNCHRONISATION MODEL

The key to synchronizing multiple, digital music streams is to know (a) the exact start time, and (b) the sample rate of each. This can be achieved in two ways: either by using a common clock (which can be used to solve both issues at once), or by independent clocks and timestamps (which allows the issues to be solved independently). Traditional mixing desks use the first approach: in the analog case, merely by having closely matched components and signal paths, and in the digital case by clocking the Analog-Digital Converters (ADC) synchronously. In the distributed sources case, as would be seen in a fully digital recording studio, either approach can be taken.

Achieving a microsecond-level master clock is not straightforward, but once it is achieved, then the synchronization problem is solved. In this work we address the more difficult case, where each ADC has its own clock, and both the start time of the stream, and the offsets between streams need to be maintained to allow accurate synchronization. We first show a general model of such a system, and then address one of the key algorithms – the real-time mixing of unsynchronized streams.

The basic model for the data flow with a single stream is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Single Stream Model.

The analog signal (from a microphone or instrument) is sampled and converted by the ADC. The time of the first sample is determined by when the software starts the ADC; the rate of the sampling is determined by both rate

selected by the software, and by the accuracy of the ADC’s internal clock. The data is then buffered in a queue to be delivered to the front-end software (responsible for relaying the audio stream). This buffer must be large enough to allow for the latency of the front-end software (to prevent buffer over-runs). The front-end then delivers the data to the network.

In this case we are considering a low-latency, local network (and not the Internet in general) – specifically the case where there are no routers in the network, so that congestion and packet prioritization are not issues. The data is then delivered to the back-end software (the mixing desk) which (a) stores the data on disk for recording and (b) delivers the data to a DAC to be converted for the monitoring function. Again, buffering to the DAC must be used to prevent buffer under-runs. A multi-stream model is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Multi-Stream Model.

Once an ADC has been started, then data will be delivered at a constant rate (dependent on the accuracy of the clock) over the data stream to the DAC. The size of this buffer is dependent on the ADC conversion rate, and the worst-case latency of the front-end software. The impact of the network is to introduce a delay in each stream which is not dependent on the data rate (it has two components: in the loss-free case, it is determined by the characteristics of the intervening network; in the lossy case, it will also be determined by the network retransmission strategy). Note that, as long as the ADC buffer never over-runs, the recording function is reliable; but the real-time monitoring function is also dependent on the network latency. It is assumed that the clocks of the source systems are synchronized (e.g. using PTP within $1\mu\text{s}$, as discussed in [22] and [23]). The ADC clocks are, however, assumed to be independent.

To synchronise streams, a timestamp is required at the start of each stream. This allows the relative offset between the streams to be identified. To maintain synchronization (in the face of clock drift between multiple ADCs) a periodic timestamp is required in each stream. Even though the data may be delivered in smaller chunks,

as determined by the ADC buffer size, and the transport protocol behavior, the stream is therefore packetized into large packets (for example, 1 second long, with a timestamp and other status information at the head of each).

In this paper, we do not address the problems in resynchronising the independent streams after the recording function (obviously this will be required for final mixing). For the real-time monitoring function, the two issues of latency and synchronization must be addressed in real-time: latency, so that the sound engineer does not see a perceivable lag between the musicians' actions and the monitored sound; and synchronization, so that volume and position artifacts are not introduced. In this paper we show some initial results, showing that the first problem is surmountable, and address in more detail the second problem of mixing multiple digital audio streams with a time delay (using an offset merge, presented in the next section).

OFFSET MERGE AND RESAMPLING

The mix function requires two (or more) audio streams to be merged with a time offset (in order to counteract the offsets in the start time of each stream). The offset may not be fixed, due to the independent nature of the ADC clocks, and so we also present a resample-and-merge algorithm for this case (note that the periodic timestamps allow this case to be identified).

We introduce a simple Offset-Merge Algorithm (OMA) for achieving this, and present some initial results. To date we have implemented 2-stream OMA – multi-stream OMA is work in progress.

Offset Merge

A simple multi-channel merge algorithm with a per-channel offset allows inter-channel synchronization to be achieved. An example of the operation of this algorithm is shown for the 2-channel case in Figure 5.

Figure 5. 2-Channel offset merge, with a 3-sample offset.

The two separate input streams are merged into a single two-channel stream as an output (which can be directly queued to the DAC). This requires that the merge buffer be at least twice the size of the output (DAC) buffer. If the offset is larger than this, then the intervening samples from the earlier channel can either be played on their own, or discarded.

Pre-Merge Resampling

Cumulative differences between input channel sampling rates can be detected by the periodic timestamps. It is assumed that the drift is less than one sample per DAC buffer size. Assuming that the sampling clocks have reasonably high accuracy (say 1 ppm) then this error will be reflected in an occasional 1-sample difference. The channel (or tracks in the case of multi-track communication) with fewer samples are re-sampled in real-time up to the larger number of samples (Figure 6 only shows 3 samples – in practice an entire buffer of say 1024 samples would be used) before being output to the monitoring DAC. Note also that, for simplicity, Diagram 5 shows an offset of 0 samples for the offset merge that follows the resampling.

Figure 6. Resampling prior to an offset merge.

The real master clock in this case is actually the DAC output clock – it is future work to adopt this algorithm to use this as the reference clock for re-sampling (i.e. all inputs streams will be candidates for re-sampling to keep in synchronization with the output DAC).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results are shown here for experiments evaluating the effectiveness of the Offset-Merge Algorithm for inter-stream synchronisation.

Experimental Setup

A Wi-Fi network was setup between two Linux nodes, with a server representing the mixing desk, and a client representing a digital, wireless microphone, as shown in Table 2.

The parameters were selected to reflect a data source of 44,100 2-byte samples per second as closely as possible. This allows a representative measurement of latency to be measured. The TCP Nagle algorithm was disabled using the TCP_PUSH protocol option to minimize network protocol latency.

Parameter	Value
Ethernet (Server-to-AP)	100 Mbps
Wi-Fi (Client-to-AP)	802.11g 36Mbps
Buffer Size	1024 bytes 512 samples
Inter-buffer delay	11 ms
Throughput	46,545 samples/s 93,090 bytes/s
Duration	400 buffers 4.4 seconds

Table 2. Configuration parameters.

Re-synchronisation

Measurements showed that channels can be successfully merged with an offset to resolve the inter-channel loss of synchronization down to single sample resolution. Fixed de-synchronisation delays were used in generating the desynchronized channels, and these were successfully removed at the merge stage. Some informal listening experiments with headphones also showed successful results.

There is significant contribution of the audio buffering to the total latency: for the 1024-byte buffer we found to be successful in preventing under-runs, this contributed 11.6ms at each end, giving a base latency of 23.2ms prior to any additional network or processing latency.

CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

Conclusions

The results of the project to date have shown the feasibility of model for a wireless studio with independently clocked digitization (ADCs) and real-time sound monitoring using off-the-shelf parts. These results can be reasonably extrapolated from a non-RT to an RT environment (such as RTLinux).

We have measured the required inter-stream synchronisation, and presented a simple algorithm for achieving this in real-time. In the context of the network and processing latencies of a standard Linux system, we have shown that with time-stamped data streams, this algorithm can execute successfully.

The project has identified a number of key additional areas to be investigated in order to determine the feasibility of a fully-digital, wireless studio (where all communication is digital). These are discussed in the next section.

Future Work

Four key issues have been identified for future work: real-time operation, a real-time wireless network, manual synchronisation controls, and automated synchronization.

Synchronisation

Inter-node synchronization can be achieved down to microsecond accuracy [22,23]. If the sound capture hard-

ware/software supports it, then they can just be synchronized simply using the inter-node synchronised clock. If not, then the latency between the ADC converting a sample and its delivery to the software layers needs to be determined. On a non-RT O/S this can be estimated from timestamping the initial ‘start’ request to the CPU; by using provided latency measures (e.g. PulseAudio has a `get_latency()` function); or by external means (e.g. a calibration signal). We plan to evaluate these three measures, and, if the third measure is required, investigate auto-calibration options.

Real-Time Operating System

The key to low latency is to minimize buffer size (which preventing underflows). In a non-RT system (such as Linux) there is significant and variable system overhead, which requires relatively large buffer sizes (e.g. up to 1024 bytes=512 samples=11.6ms). With this buffer size at the recording ADC and the playback DAC, the latency is already in the region of 30ms – well above the 10ms target figure. This could be significantly mitigated by use of a real-time platform. We plan to investigate the use of real-time processes under Linux to see how well they perform; we also plan to experiment with an embedded system (powered by an Atmel CPU and a suitable RTOS), providing a guaranteed latency to hardware events in the order of 10’s of microseconds. We plan to investigate this using a real-time operating system to investigate the minimum buffer size that can operate with no underflows.

Real-Time Wireless Networking

TCP and Wi-Fi are not intended for real-time operation – and again, buffering has to be used to prevent data underflows. This, in general, requires another 1024-byte buffer, this time at application level at the playback end, adding another 11.6ms to the latency. We intend to experiment with two alternatives here: one is the use of the RTP transport protocol (though for direct node-to-node communication, with a very low level of packet loss/retransmission and no congestion, we don’t expect this to provide significant improvements).

We intend to experiment with UDP and a customized re-transmission policy that ignores congestion, and focuses on short-latency retransmissions.

Additional experiments are planned using a dedicated, point-to-point wireless protocol in association with an RTOS, and a simplified transport protocol that handles packet loss aggressively but not congestion (as in the configurations envisaged, all communication is node-to-node with no intervening routers and possibly a single high-performance Ethernet switch).

Resampling

The resampling operation has not yet been verified – but as we see this as purely a monitoring (rather than a recording) process, we don’t expect it to cause any significant problems (and certainly no loss of quality of the rec-

orded signal). We plan to experiment with up-sampling and down-sampling to determine whether this causes a perceivable effect to the monitored signal.

Automated Synchronisation

A number of papers have reported ways of automatically determining the time-shift between two channels by correlating features in the sound streams, for example [19]. We plan to experiment with incorporating these into the offset merge operation to determine their effectiveness at the level of resolution required (i.e. approximately 2 samples).

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